

Language Barriers In Learning Development: A Voice Of Simplification

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Abstract. This study described how the policy on intensifying the medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas was carried out by teachers using the English language during the School Year 2022-2023. A qualitative research design was used, and assumptions regarding selecting participants and ethics in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data were considered. Respondents were the parents who were purposely selected through referrals and using facilitating questions to draw out narratives on their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms and further learning insights given their professional growth and pedagogical accountability to learners' development skills and ability to develop and improve academic performance and despite of all instructional interventions delivered, and where learning generally happens not only in school but at home as well is being considered to be explored. Teachers' experiences with language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners were challenged by limited language barriers, vocabulary gaps, and complex sentence structures. Coping mechanisms have been found to cope through intensification of teaching strategies, community immersion, and engagement activities with parents. Educational insights were found to redirect attitudes toward adaptation, recommend actions for policy, and keep the right track for follow-up. Future direction may provide an opportunity to translate the findings into practical actions and interventions at the district, school, and classroom levels. Continued research and collaboration among stakeholders contribute to improving educational practices, policies, and support systems for young learners and their families.

KEY WORDS

1. language barriers 2. learning development 3. voice of simplification

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1. Introduction

Language barriers in learning development can be seen as a voice of simplification, indicating the need for clear communication and accessible educational approaches. When learners face language barriers, whether due to limited proficiency in the language of instruction or the presence of multiple languages in their learning environment, it becomes crucial to simplify language use and promote effective communication. This can involve using plain language, visual aids, and gestures to support understanding. Emphasizing simplicity in instruction and materials can break down language barriers and create a more inclusive learning environment, allowing all learners to engage in the learning process actively. By acknowledging lan-

guage barriers as a voice of simplification, educators and policymakers can work towards creating language-inclusive classrooms that value diverse linguistic backgrounds and promote equitable access to quality education. Teaching through English Medium of Instruction (EMI) is a theory-based pedagogy adopted in many European and Asian countries as a strategic initiative in educational internationalization. Teaching through the English Medium of Instruction is a reasonably new learning delivery system. It has arisen as part of an emergent dynamic: the globalization of education within a global economy. It is described and commonly accepted as the use of the English language to teach academic subjects in countries or jurisdictions where the first language of most of the population is not English. Thus, it is not a significant consideration in countries where English is the national language. Instead, it arises as the “business” of the rest of the world when governments and the education systems that they manage pressure teaching staff to use English as the medium of instruction to raise their domestic students’ English proficiency and make their classes accessible to international student groups (Alansari and Rubie-Davies, 2021). Teaching via EMI across Europe dates back to the 1990s and is evidenced in the Bologna Declaration as an objective in EU tertiary education reform. EMI was a strategic move for EU countries to internationalize their universities’ curricula to pursue accreditation in the fast-developing, globalized world. With the increasingly competitive marketing of higher education in recent years, some central Asian countries and regions such as China, Vietnam, Korea, and Taiwan have been swiftly moving toward EMI delivery in their higher education sector for various but comparable reasons. For example, the Chinese Ministry of Education (MOE) has recently introduced policies prioritizing EMI teaching in higher education as part of the country’s strategic plan for developing its World First Class University and First Class Academic Discipline Construction. This is an element of the nation’s ambition to make China the top destination for international students (Hendrikx et al., 2021). In the Philippines, the Department of Education stipulated DepEd Order No. 36, S 2006, related to the implementing rules and regulations on Executive Order No. 210 on establishing the policy to strengthen the use of the English Language as a Medium of Instruction in the Educational System. Teachers are advised to comply with the existing medium of instruction per learning area, Filipino and English, which shall remain the language of instruction. This is to challenge the schools regarding the quality of curriculum management and assessment delivery throughout the country. In the DepEd Region XI, the Curriculum and Learning Management Division released a Regional Memorandum CLMD-2023-031 directing a policy on intensifying the medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas. Further, bilingual education policy and the local languages are used as auxiliary languages of instruction for formal education and the alternative learning system. The use of the stated medium of instruction should be intensified as English for the subjects in English Science, Mathematics, TLE and Filipino for the subjects in Filipino, Araling Panlipunan Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao and MAPEH (CLMD-2023-031). Using the mother tongue as the language of instruction beginning in Grade 1 is now recognized as the most effective way to improve student learning and shall also serve as a vital bridge to learning a second language better and faster (Farnazo, 2023). Such is because some stakeholders have expressed their frustrations that their children in school have difficulty learning due to language being a barrier. Some parents give feedback that their children find it hard to understand because they cannot speak Visayan or their mother tongue, thus requesting the DepEd to consider English as part of the medium of Instruction.

This made the teacher develop strategies for the transition of the terms in the lesson and content that must be done from the mother tongue to Filipino and English. This is a challenge to many schools in Marilog District A because most of the learners belong to the Indigenous Peoples Group, and their first language is not Visayan but a language based on the tribe they belong to. Thus, teachers in Marilog District A have to brace themselves for this policy, taking into account the directives of the Regional Office's policy. Thus, this paper is presented. The purpose of this phenomenological research study was to describe how the policy on intensification of medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas carried out by teachers using the English language in teaching during School Year 2022-2023. At this stage in the re-

search, teachers' lived experiences, their coping mechanisms given challenges encountered, and insights are generally defined as their professional growth and pedagogical accountability to learners' development skills and ability to develop and improve academic performance despite all instructional interventions delivered, and where learning generally happens not only in school but at home as well as being considered to be explored.

1.1. Research Questions—This study aimed to understand and describe teachers' experiences in adopting a policy on intensifying medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas in the Elementary Schools of Marilog A District, Davao City Schools Division, during SY 2022-2023. It sought to answer to the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners?
- (2) How do teachers address the language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the experiences of the teachers?

The results of this study will be beneficial and provide significant inputs and bases in the delivery and management of curriculum implementation and assessment given the quality assurance assessment cycle for schools to consider curriculum of Key Stage 1 and 2 learners given facilitation of instruction be improved amongst schools in Marilog A District, Davao City Division. Thus, the following stakeholders will benefit from the study outputs. School Principals. The school heads/principals set the management and eventually direct the teachers and other stakeholders to improve performance, whether in the school's operation or curriculum management. The school principal is expected to manage the curriculum implementation for kindergarten to grade 6 learners to make teachers sound and well in the skills intended to be mastered through a face-to-face learning modality. Thus, the results of the study will provide

insights to school heads of Marilog A District schools, Davao City, as to how teachers are well prepared in the adoption of a policy on intensification of the medium of instruction in teaching specific learning area, improve delivery of curriculum through its extent of management. Implementation can be of help as an intervention to help learners and teachers enhance their academic and professional skills. Teachers. As generalists in the elementary curriculum, teachers are expected to teach all learning areas following the Essential Learning Competencies in Kinder to Grade 6. Further, follow directions based on the provided plan that is comprehensive and doable at each time and cost given the guidelines of MTB-MLE. In this context, teachers ensure that their efforts to implement and facilitate learners' learning will not be in vain. Thus, adopting a policy on intensifying the medium of instruction in teaching specific learn-

ing areas must be mastered. The study's results will show teachers whether using English as a medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas can make facilitation more effective, and learners will become more productive and contribute to their performance development skills. Parents play significant roles in their children's language skills development. The study's results will give insights and enlightenment to the PTA and the school governing council members. They will also advocate for empowerment to continuously improve the school's process, performance, and academic achievement through full participation in the whole cycle process of learners' learning development. Future Researchers. Implications based on the study's generated results will provide more information to future researchers to replicate the practices to be discovered in the proposed study. These practices include the type and approaches of curriculum implementation and the efficiency elements in improving the quality delivery of education outputs through the process introduced in the MELCs. The following terms are variables used in the study and definitions by the concept and operation is presented according to how the terms were used in the study context. This served as a reference in analyzing and interpreting the results to come up with meaningful implications for a better understanding and recommendations. Language Barriers. The term refers to the latent variable that is set in the context of the study. Language barriers usually occur when two people who speak different languages cannot understand one another, and there is a breakdown in language and communication. It causes misunderstandings and misinterpretations among coworkers, straining their interpersonal relationships. However, language is needed for any verbal, non-verbal, or even sign language. The inability to communicate using language makes way for language barriers. Language differences are the most obvious barrier to communication, which occurs when two

people speak different languages and cannot communicate. Linguistic ability: Even when two people speak the same language, there may be significant differences in their linguistic ability. In this study, the term is used as a latent variable, and experiences, challenges, and learning insights were taken from personal interviews among teachers. They are learning Development. The term refers to working with students and staff to develop academic practices, with a main focus on students developing academic practices. In this study, the term is used as the latent variable where teachers adopt a policy on intensification of using English as a medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas, and assistance is expected through school heads' involvement and participation in educational processes and activities shared by the School through providing technical assistance. Thus, this will be the basis for the parents to see clear directions on how to make learning more fun for children.

1.2. *Review of Significant Literature*—

This section reviews literature and studies on the socio-educational journey of parents in supporting young learners' multilanguage education, arranged according to variables and indicators in the conceptual framework.

1.2.1. *Language Barriers in Learning Development*—Language barriers hinder elementary learners' ability to comprehend and communicate effectively in the classroom. Limited proficiency in the language of instruction, vocabulary gaps, and complex sentence structures are significant challenges affecting engagement, comprehension, and academic performance (Goh Luen, 2021; Mncube et al., 2021). Educators can address these through targeted support programs, simplified language use, and inclusive environments (Veliz Veliz-Campos, 2021; Al-Riyami et al., 2022).

1.2.2. *Teachers' Role in Addressing Barriers*—Teachers employ strategies like active coping, mindfulness, and differentiated instruc-

tion to address language barriers. Positive strategies, such as engaging classroom activities and parental involvement, significantly enhance learners' development. Administrative support and community immersion further improve teaching outcomes (Byrd, 2017; Amateur, 2021; Cao et al., 2022). Effective English-medium instruction (EMI) incorporates adaptive teaching practices and intercultural competence (Wang, 2023; Hosan et al., 2022).

1.2.3. Vocabulary and Sentence Structures—Limited vocabulary and complex sentence structures impact learners' reading fluency, comprehension, and communication. Explicit instruction, visual aids, and vocabulary-building exercises can mitigate these challenges. Educators should also gradually introduce complex sentence patterns to improve understanding (Muttaqin et al., 2022; Al-Jarf, 2022).

1.2.4. Addressing Multilingualism in Education—Multilingual education policies often face tensions between promoting English-medium instruction and preserving native languages. Effective policy actions should balance these needs while enhancing teachers' pedagogical skills and supporting Indigenous learners. Community engagement and responsive pedagogies can help bridge cultural gaps and foster inclusivity (Malcolm et al., 2020; Eduardo Gabriel, 2021; Erdocia, 2019).

1.2.5. Coping and Adaptation Strategies—Teachers often face stress from student behavior, curriculum changes, and language barriers. Coping mechanisms like mindfulness, professional development, and shared responsibility improve teaching outcomes and student satisfaction (Skelly Estrada-Chichon, 2021; Sarzhanova et al., 2023). Adaptation mechanisms for domestic and international students highlight the need for inclusive practices in English-medium instruction settings (Volkova Kolesov, 2022).

1.2.6. Policy Implications—Effective bilingual and multilingual education policies

should align with cooperative learning strategies and professional learning development (PLD) opportunities. These strategies improve student engagement and educational outcomes across diverse curriculum areas (Alansari et al., 2021).

1.3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the theory of Lord William Bentinck (1831), who took control of Mysore on the grounds of misgovernance. He passed the English Education Act 1835, which replaced Persian with English in the higher courts. Lord William Bentinck is known as India's liberal Governor-General. He is credited with significant social and educational reforms in India, including the abolition of Sati, the suppression of female infanticide and Thuggee, the abolition of lawlessness, and the abolition of human sacrifices. Lord William Bentinck introduced English as a medium of higher education in India on the advice of Thomas Babington Macaulay, his council member. In 1835, faced with urgent petitions from editors of English and vernacular newspapers, Governor-General Bentinck agreed to revise press laws. The English Education Act, although it was brought to effect by Lord William Bentinck, was based upon the advice and ideas of Thomas Macaulay, and hence, these two should not be confused with each other. The English Education Act took a less hostile attitude toward traditional education (Cankaya, 2017). According to Lord William Bentinck, the medium of instruction is the language the teacher uses to teach. Teaching the language, or educational content, through the target language increases the amount of exposure the learner gets to it and the opportunities they have to communicate in it and, therefore, develop their control of it. Following instructions is a crucial ability to practice in everyday life. Within an academic setting, following instructions can influence grades, learning subject matter, and correctly executing skills (Hendriks et al., 2021).

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

In the Philippines, English Medium Instruction (EMI) refers to using the English language to teach academic subjects (other than English itself) in countries where most of the population does not speak English as their first language. English serves as the medium of instruction in our country. It is the language of the academe, and therefore, it can reach many people. As it is used in school, English helps mold the minds of the children who want to become the future of the Philippines. The medium of instruction is the language used by the teacher to teach. Teaching the language, or educational content, through the target language increases the amount of exposure the learner gets to it and the opportunities they have to communicate in it, and therefore, develop their control of it. In the Philippines, English prevails as the predominant medium of instruction. It is used more in teaching than the national language, Filipino. All subjects except the subject of Filipino are taught in English. English medium in schools allows children to communicate more efficiently

with people worldwide. This also prepares children for future jobs where English will be the primary language of communication. In this study, the primary concern of the current paper is to discuss English medium instruction (EMI, henceforth) in all aspects, focusing on the challenges and difficulties reported by students and teachers based on the relevant research studies. As EMI is gaining the most significant importance among researchers, policymakers, and educators, it was crucial to reveal the main instructional problems during the implementation process to understand them clearly. Figure 1 shows the interconnection between the two research questions: language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners and teachers' addressing the language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners, which would result in the common denominator: Insights Learned from secondary school teachers' experiences and their understanding of the teachers' experiences.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript.

This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—This study explores four philosophical assumptions that provide the framework of understanding for the proposed qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. Each seeks to answer a different question about the observed phenomenon through a different perspective. **Ontology.** An ontology describes things, relationships, and their characteristics, usually in a well-bounded domain, for example, ecology or astronomy. It was, in part, a taxonomy, a graph structure that describes the hierarchical relationship of a group of things. This assumption deals with the nature of reality. An ontological approach looks at the things the data is about and uses them as the basis for the structure of the data. Ontology is concerned with the nature of reality. There is one defined reality: fixed, measurable, and observable. Given the complexity of the world within which nursing research is conducted, researchers using qualitative methodologies have had to grapple with this issue. Ontology helps researchers recognize how certain they can be about the nature and existence of objects they are researching (Creswell, 2012). **Epistemology.** Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), shared that Epistemological assumptions deal with knowledge gained through an empathic understanding of participants' lived social realities; science aims to describe people's subjective lived realities, experiences, and understandings. Researchers must decide what knowledge they want to gather about the social world and how, but epistemological assumptions, values, and methods may be inextricably intertwined. The theory of knowledge deals with how knowledge is gathered and from which sources. In research terms, the view of the world and expertise strongly influence the interpretation of data, and therefore, the philosophical standpoint should be made clear from the beginning. **Epistemology** is critical because it influences how researchers frame their research in their attempts to discover knowledge. By looking at the relationship between a subject and an object, we can explore the idea of epistemology and how it influences research design. **Axiology.** Axiology is an ethical issue that must be considered when planning a research proposal. It considers the philosophical approach to making value decisions or the right choices (Finnis, 1980). The axiological assumption here was that objectivity is reasonable and subjectivity is bad (Creswell Poth, 2018). The researchers' worldviews influenced the types of questions asked. The analysis of the findings and extrapolation of themes are also influenced by the researchers' values, personal experiences, and worldviews. In simple terms, axiology focuses on the value of research. This is important because values affect how research was conducted and the value of research findings. Axiology has relevance to the field of qualitative research since it has a direct bearing on the ethical context of research, offers an essential basis for making explicit the assumptions of different research paradigms, and provides the foundation for understanding the process of the addition to knowledge. **Rhetoric.** Rhetoric refers to studying and using written, spoken, and visual language. It investigates how language organizes and maintains social groups, constructs meanings and identities, coordinates behavior, mediates power, produces change, and creates knowledge. It is a theory capable of analyzing public understanding and an activity capable of making it. In its analytical role, rhetoric reveals two dominant models of public awareness: the deficit model and the contextual

model. In rhetorical methods, a critic analyzes single or multiple texts to express an informed preference, to understand how the texts fit into a larger social, political, historical, or economic framework, to unpack meaning, and to give context to the text. The presented philosophical assumptions are all relevant in the proposed study, for this makes the researcher strengthen the foundation of analysis given principles and their significance in the study's conduct. The context speaks of the parents' socio-educational scaffold that facilitates learners' beginning in their learning processes. It will make parents explore their challenges and learn from those worth emulating. Given the ontological perspective, the researcher gained from various connections of the experiences and challenges encountered by the participants, thus giving an idea to lay more foundation using the epistemological principle where knowledge of the body has been gained through strong supports and claims by the phenomenon. However, as the details of the circumstances were discovered, axiology came to its function of filtering the meaning beyond the subjectivity of the participants. This calls for the reactivation of ethical standards, thus protecting the participants' personal views that may influence the wholeness of the phenomenon. After all was given, rhetoric put everything in place and order. Thus, this proposed research gained confidence in applying a qualitative process to establish the latent variables worthy of sharing for future research. In this regard, I would utilize the qualitative research method of phenomenology to explore the experiences, challenges, and insights of the teachers who utilized outdoor learning to develop scientific understanding and others involved in the scenario implemented crisis-management strategies. This method was advantageous for addressing complex issues and understanding real-life experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—This proposed qualitative research assumes phenomeno-

logical research, a qualitative research approach that seeks to understand and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon. Phenomenology as a method has four characteristics: descriptive, reduction, essence, and intentionality. The approach investigates the everyday experiences of human beings while suspending the researchers' preconceived assumptions about the phenomenon. The phenomenological approach was a qualitative inquiry that emphasizes experiential, lived aspects of a particular construct—how the phenomenon was experienced when it occurs rather than what is thought about this experience or the meaning ascribed to it subsequently. Phenomenology helps understand the meaning of people's lived experiences. A phenomenological study explores what people experience and focuses on their experience of phenomena. There are two main approaches to phenomenology: descriptive and interpretive. Descriptive phenomenology was developed by Edmund Husserl and interpretive by Martin Heidegger (Connelly 2010), as cited by Creswell (2014). Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories (Moustakas, 1994, as quoted by Creswell, 2014). In this process, the research brackets set aside their own experiences to understand those of the participants in the study. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, lower validity and reliability levels compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Lotich, 2011). The application of the research design in the context of the study suggests appropriateness in the advancement of exploration and description by narrating personal experiences in all given related circumstances. Through using the lens (Lahey and

Cohen, 2020) corroborated that the value of phenomenology was that it prioritizes and investigates how human beings experience the world, which would be explored in this study that instructional delivery was assumed to be effective in augmenting learners' performance outcome. The phenomenon shall be unfolded and be experienced authentically by the learners. Through the selected design, the researcher can generate original experiences. The standards may not be adopted, but variations of learning outcomes are appreciated and meaningful.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—According to Creswell (2014), the overall strategy chosen to integrate the different components of the study coherently and logically was called research design. Research design constituted the blueprint for collecting, measuring, and analyzing the data, ensuring that the researcher effectively addressed the research problem. The type of design the researcher used also determined the research problem. This research intended to use a qualitative research method that engages a phenomenological qualitative design. Creswell (2013), as cited by Chambers (2013), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the specific phenomenon. After the panel members approved the thesis proposal in March 2023, the researcher started preparing for data gathering. She prepared a letter to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent requesting permission to conduct the study using the procedures presented. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data was then read and reread and was culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. The researcher constructed the universal sense of the

event and situation through this process. Such a series of activities were done during the days of March 2023. In addition, as cited by Chambers (2013), Maxwell (2013) also added that, with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempted to extract untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. Creswell (2012) also claimed that qualitative research primarily uses interviews. They occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to investigate their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees would say (McNamara, 1999). Based on Quad's (2016) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher was required to have a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study should be individuals who have experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was challenging. Since this study focused on exploring and assessing the teachers' experience and challenges in enhancing classroom instruction in the new face-to-face classes, the researcher intended to employ phenomenological qualitative research methods.

2.4. *Ethical Considerations* —The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study; hence, adherence to the policy set by the Rizal Memorial Colleges research committee corresponding requirements will be religiously secured to ensure the appropriateness of the process based on the standards, thus mitigating possible risks such as physical psychological and socio-economic affectations were avoided. Proper authorization and consent were also obtained from the respondents of the study to ensure that all their rights would be fully protected, specifically in handling the data, however, not limited to; Voluntary Participation. The researcher considered several ethical considerations to ensure the study was conducted appropriately. To comply with ethical considerations when conducting research, all participants were provided with informed consent to participate in the study. This indicated that the participation was voluntary (Lotich, 2011). Privacy and Confidentiality. The study's participants' profiles were kept confidential to protect their rights. Privacy and confidentiality were observed explicitly through the presentation and discussion of results (Koenigna MacMillan, 2004). They informed the Consent Process. The researcher observed and adhered to the proper protocol for the recruitment process. Initially, the researcher sought the permission of the school division superintendent to conduct the study. Then, the endorsement from the said office was submitted to the school principal, where the study will be conducted (Lotich, 2011). Thus, the researcher also ensured that the protocol and reminders given by the office of the SDS were observed correctly. This includes the observance of the time-on-task policy. It was further explained to the participants that their information would remain private and confidential and that the specific content of individual surveys would only be discussed with the research adviser. The research adviser and the participants are unknown to each other. In the final report, the identity of the respondents was removed, and pseudonyms were used for the participants. While sharing the purpose of the study with the participants, the researcher also shared their background and some of the researcher's personal stories as a professional woman in the teaching industry. This helped build trust and, in turn, encouraged the respondents to answer the survey honestly. Risks. Moreover, the researcher informed the participants that participating in the study would not bring any foreseeable risks to their health or well-being. Thus, they were told that if they became upset or distressed as a result of answering the questions that are part of the researcher's standard battery, then the researcher would have helped them obtain a referral for the respondent to see a trained professional who could help process these feelings (Lotich, 2011). Benefits. Further, the study's observable benefits were immediately disseminated to the stakeholders. The study's findings generated important facts for enhancing young learners' well-being (Koenig MacMillan, 2004). The study's findings served as the basis for educational institutions to focus on creating a learning environment that enhances students' ability to become more productive and active. Also, this study provided meaningful information to school heads and teachers as they developed plans to implement change best and develop learners' multilanguage learning development. Plagiarism. Furthermore, the researcher strictly adhered to other ethical issues, which include plagiarism, fabrication, and falsification (Lakey and Cohen, 2020). The researcher ensured that the resources being used in this study were cited correctly. The authors' ideas are paraphrased and properly synthesized to avoid plagiarism. No fabrication or inclusion of data, survey, or enactment ever arises in data gathering. The researcher made conclusions that were only found from the study results. In the event of any unintentional plagiarized, fab-

ricated, or falsified ideas, the researcher immediately revised the manuscript (Lotich, 2011). Fabrication. The researcher guaranteed that deceit and conflict of interest provisions will be strictly observed. The researcher assured the participants that the study was done honestly and transparently. Evidence shows that the benefit of misleading the participants outweighs any potential harm to them (Creswell, 2014). The researcher satisfactorily assisted the participants and discussed the study's process and outcome. They were given a general idea of what the researcher was investigating and why such a study was conducted. Their role and contribution to the study were promptly explained. Falsification. This study complied with the citation rules set based on the APA 7th edition citation format to avoid misrepresenting work or altering any data gathered in the study (Cohen, 2020). The data and information were written and presented the most accurately. Conflict of Interest. The researcher ensures that conflict of interest (COI) in this study is highly observed (Lotich, 2011). There was no set of conditions for professional judgment concerning primary interest, as the participants' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by secondary interests, such as financial or academic gains or any forms of recognition. Deceit. The writings of this paper would not be utilized in any form of untruthfulness to harm anyone, especially the participants, since all information written was checked and validated by the panel of thesis experts (Lakey and Cohen, 2020). Permission from the Organization/Location. Before the study, the researcher provides a letter to conduct a study duly signed by the Dean of Graduate School to the Schools Division Superintendent. Then, the reply from the office allowing the researcher to conduct the study is delivered to the school principal where the study was conducted. Authorship. Finally, upon the approval of the final version to be published, the researcher considered for the authorship the adviser and a few

other individuals, such as colleagues who gave substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data and drafting the manuscript or revising it critically for important intellectual content as co-authors (Lotich, 2011). Participants can contact the researcher at the mobile number and email address provided on the informed consent form if they have questions, concerns, or complaints about the research. The researcher also ensured that the study's benefits would be shared during meetings and conferences with stakeholders as part of the audience.

2.5. *Research Participants*—The respondents of the proposed study were the Elementary School Teachers in Marilog A District, Davao City Division. Inclusions of the participants are assumed and expected to be teaching at the elementary level in the respective schools. The researcher randomly looked for good oral communication teachers sometime in the second week of April 2023. She used referral sampling to determine which teachers became participants in the interview during data gathering. Once participants were determined, they were informed through an online platform or text / direct personal messages about the purpose and importance of the study. The researcher further observed ethics in research that may have paved the way for a teacher-participant to decline, and thus, corresponding forms of consent/decline were provided. This was deliberated through the coaching of the thesis adviser. In this manner, the research ethics standards, as part of the policy of the Rizal Memorial Colleges Graduate School, were strictly followed. Thus, observance of health protocol was likewise implemented based on the Executive Orders released by the local community leaders of Marilog A and the regional government of Davao City to avoid possible contamination and lower the risk of contamination. All interviews were taped, recorded, and transcribed verbatim afterward,

as this was protected against bias and provided a permanent record of what was and was not said. It helped make 'field notes' during and immediately after each interview about observations, thoughts, and ideas about the interview, which helped in the data analysis process. A good quality multi-directional external microphone was used to record focus groups, as internal microphones help cope with the variation in volume of different speakers. If observers were present, they were introduced to the participants as someone who were just there to observe and would often take notes. Videotaping requires more than one camera to capture the whole group and additional operational personnel in the room (Chadwick et al., 2008).

2.6. Role of the Researcher—Meanwhile, Fink (2000) suggested that the roles of the researcher are to thematize, develop the design, conduct interviews, transcribe, analyze, verify, and report. Further, the main task was transforming data to live the participants' experiences. This was to bring an individual's experiences into words by gathering facts and information in verbatim form, then attempt to understand those experiences based on the statements, and finally, develop and categorize themes, which will be the basis for founding a comprehensive phenomenological description of the conducted study. In this sense, in qualitative research, the "researcher" is the instrument herself (Starks and Trinidad, 2007). The author further emphasized that precision is essential, and several lenses and degrees of sensitivity must be considered, especially when collecting, viewing, analyzing, and reporting the data. In this study, I was considered part of one of the instruments. As a proponent, you need to describe relevant aspects, including any biases and assumptions, expectations, and experiences, to qualify your ability to conduct the research. Asking probing questions to the participants, listening well, thinking, and analyzing to get into deeper analysis provided an opportunity to

build a picture and draw out ideas and theories from various sources and responses.

2.7. Research Instrument—The researcher applied qualitative analysis to establish the study's credibility, transferability, and dependability. The participants' experiences were collected and investigated through one-on-one non-structured interviews, audio tapes, field notes, and peer debriefing. Interview Guide. In an unstructured interview, the researcher prepared five open-ended questions to gather additional information and supporting answers to validate the study's findings. The interview questions were inclined to the components contained in the questionnaire. Unstructured interviews were not reflected by preconceived theories or ideas and were performed with little or no organization. Their use was generally only with significant depth, or virtually nothing was known about the subject area, or a different perspective of a known subject area was required. Moreover, the research interview explores individuals' views, experiences, beliefs, and motivations on specific matters. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, were believed to provide a deeper understanding of social phenomena than would be obtained from purely quantitative methods, such as questionnaires (Stewart et al., 2008). A guide question was a questionnaire that was carefully designed, written down, and tested to individual respondents' queries to gather information in a research study (Enon, 2008). The open-ended questions allowed the respondents to give further opinions by qualifying or substantiating their answers. They were also intended to tap as much information as possible from the different categories of respondents. O'Leary (2014) added that questionnaires have many uses, most notably in discovering the masses' thinking.

2.8. Data Gathering Procedure—This research set the procedure and discussed the steps in data gathering. It detailed the content when getting permission to conduct the study, the dis-

tribution and retrieval of the questionnaire, and the collation and statistical treatment of data. Permission to conduct the study. On the first week of February 2023, before data gathering, the researcher prepared the necessary conditions to observe the health protocol policy of the Local Government of Marilog District, Davao City. Ethics in data collection was assumed to have been appropriately followed. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel members on March 2023, through the Dean of the Graduate School's approval and the guidance of the thesis adviser, the researcher prepared a letter of permission to conduct the study through data gathering. The researcher sought permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent through the channel for approval to collect data from the chosen respondents. She then proceeded to Schools, handling the letter of acceptance to the School Heads and, thus, made connections with the teachers. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared Google Sheets and some hard copies to distribute the guide questions. This was sent through a link to the randomly selected participants through email addresses and personal meetings. Once data was gathered and completed, the researcher double-checked its responses, ensuring every statement survey was answered. This prepared me for the next step: collating and treating the data gathered. Collation and statistical treatment of data. In May 2023, given the premise that the data gathered were complete, the researcher sought the guidance of the thesis adviser and treated through an expert in data analysis. This went on until the last days of September 2023, and it was expected that all statement problems posed generated answers. This gave meaningful insights into the discussions and interpretations of results.

2.9. *Data Analysis*—Data analysis involves making sense of text and image data. It consists of preparing the data for analysis, con-

ducting different analyses, moving deeper and deeper into understanding the data, representing the data, and interpreting its more significant meaning. Creswell (2014) pointed out that analyzing data involves collecting open-ended data based on asking general questions and developing an analysis from the information supplied by the participants. The steps to be followed are linear in that the approach is building from the bottom to the top. In this sense, the researcher organized and prepared the data for analysis. These were transcribing interviews, scanning material, and typing filed-up notes or sorting and Ullrich et al. (2012) also added that due to the characteristics that underlie qualitative research, this was the subject of constant questioning regarding its scientific rigor, which was linked to the reliability, validity, and generality criteria used in its development. However, these criticisms build on quantitative assumptions, which do not respond to qualitative research objectives that seek to understand, analyze, and describe a given event rather than to measure or quantify it. Moreover, Heale and Noble (2019) mentioned that triangulation in a research study increases the credibility and validity of research findings. Credibility refers to trustworthiness and how believable a study is; validity concerns how much a study accurately reflects or evaluates the concept or ideas being investigated. Triangulation can help overcome fundamental biases arising from using a single process or observer by combining theories, methods, or observers in a research study. Environmental triangulation involves using different locations, settings, and other critical factors related to the study's environment, such as the time, day, or season. The key is identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. Validity has been established if the findings remain the same under varying ecological conditions. It was only used when it was likely that environmental factors may influence the findings.

Thematic Content Analysis. Thematic Content Analysis (TCA), as Anderson (1998) mentioned, is a descriptive presentation of qualitative data. Qualitative data may take the form of interview transcripts collected from research participants or other identified texts that reflect experientially on the topic of study. While video, image, and other forms of data may accompany textual data, this description of Thematic Content Analysis was limited to textual data. Thematic Content Analysis portrays the thematic content of interview transcripts by identifying common themes in the texts provided for analysis. It was the most foundational qualitative analytic procedure and informs all qualitative methods. The researcher's epistemological stance is objective or objectivistic when conducting a Thematic Content Analysis. The researcher groups and distills a list of common themes from the texts to express the commonality of voices across participants. Every reasonable attempt is made to employ names for themes from the actual words of participants and to group themes in a manner that directly reflects the texts as a whole. While sorting and naming themes requires some interpretation, the said interpretation is kept to a minimum. The researcher's feelings and thoughts about the themes or what the Thematic Content Analysis themes may signify were mainly irrelevant to a Thematic Content Analysis (Anderson, 1998) also affirmed. In analyzing the data, the researcher adopted the steps utilized by Anderson (1998). Before beginning a Thematic Content Analysis, the researcher makes multiple copies of the interview transcript or other extant text, including post-interview notes as relevant and stipulated in the Methodology. Next, the researcher marks all descriptions pertinent to the topic of inquiry with a Highlighter. From the highlighted areas, mark each distinct unit of meaning. This means that a break or change in meaning separates units. However, the researcher retains all information relevant to understanding a meaning unit within the meaning

unit. Units may vary in text length. Label each pile as initial categories or themes using keywords or phrases copied from highlighted texts. Revise categories as you continue to code data. Then, obvious information needs to be included in the text. In that case, the researcher would identify categories that are missing and would go through the entire interview transcript, identifying distinct units, grouping and regrouping similar and dissimilar units, and re-labeling categories for each additional interview transcript (or other texts), using the Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) as indicated on the steps highlighted above. Afterward, when all thematic content Analyses are complete, the researcher reads each thematic content analysis separately. While retaining meaning units, combine categories or themes for all interview transcripts and notes. Collapse or subdivide categories as appropriate—re-label categories as applicable. After a few days, I reread the total categories. Consider whether too many or too few categories made sense of the interview transcripts given on the topic. Redo all the instructions until the researcher was satisfied that the categories reflected the interview transcripts as a whole. The researcher read through all the data and began the detailed analysis with a coding process, in which themes were developed based on the description represented in the qualitative narratives. Finally, the researcher made an interpretation or meaning of the data by asking what lessons were learned, which captures the essence of the data collection and analysis process. These lessons could be the researcher's interpretation, couched in the understanding that the inquiry brings to the study.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—This study's trustworthiness was established to ensure the rigor of the research at hand. Common critiques of qualitative research focus on validity and reliability; however, the author presented the study's trustworthiness anchored in Starks and Trinidad (2007). Guba (1985) emphasizes

that qualitative research should embody credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility refers to internal validity and concerns about how congruent the findings are with reality. Lincoln and Guba (1985), as cited by Creswell (2014), emphasize that credibility in a study ensures the correctness of the data, which was the most important factor in trustworthiness. As a researcher, I established credibility in my study by using the triangulation method, anchored to the suggestion of Shenton (2004), as cited by Creswell (2013)—strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. The triangulation method was a strategy used to gather data from many sources. It can be done through interviews, focus group discussions, observation, and document analysis (Starks and Trinidad (2007). As a researcher, the Triangulation method is used by affixing the interview transcript to collect different data from different perspectives of the study's informants. Moreover, to further establish credibility, member-checking has been employed to ensure that the data gathered was transparent to the study's key informants. As researchers, key informants were asked if what was recorded during the interview was the same as their responses. After the participants had confirmed, they signed a member-checking form to confirm the validity of the data. Further, establishing transferability would also be considered as I accomplish this study. According to Lincoln and Lotich (2011), cited by Creswell (2014), transferability refers to the degree to which the study's results can be generalized and used in other settings with similar contexts. Researchers can establish transferability when they thoroughly discuss the research context's description and the assumptions central to the research. To ensure transferability, the researcher made sure that the job described the context of the issue under study to give readers interested in the same survey a general idea of the context and gave references as they transferred

data. Dependability in research was also a must. Dependability entails thorough coverage of the research procedures. This entails that thorough documentation on how the study is carried out is established in the study. This allows people outside the research to follow the steps taken in conducting the survey (Lotich (2011), cited by Creswell (2014). Moreover, Lakey and Cohen (2020) posited that dependability in a study includes detailed coverage of the methodology and methods employed, which allows readers to assess whether the study's conduct follows appropriate research practices. As a researcher, dependability was necessary in conducting the study by clearly describing the research design and procedures. Lastly, a researcher must ensure the study's confirmability. Confirmability, as Smith (2013) posited, focuses on how the researcher establishes the degree to which the findings of an inquiry function solely of the respondents and are not influenced by the researcher's biases, motivations, and perspectives. To achieve confirmability, as a researcher, I demonstrated that the results are linked to the conclusions in a way replicating as a process. The informants are the sole sources of the gathered data and inflict no biases or personal perspectives on the phenomenon under study. Further, an audit trail, which traces the research process, the action taken, and the procedures being followed (Lakey and Cohen, 2020), was also used. Ethical Considerations. Ethics and appropriate behavior shall be taken seriously by the researcher when dealing with selected participants and must be observed; therefore, ethical considerations must be considered. These moral considerations should emphasize social value, informed consent form, participant vulnerability, risk, benefits and safety, privacy, and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the research, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement (Creswell, 2013; Smith, 2013). Social value. Social value refers to the study's relevance to existing social

or health problems, such as the results are expected to bring about a better understanding of related issues or continue to promote the well-being of individuals, their families, and communities. The social value of the study is appreciated through the observed change in behavior among parents in adopting the implications of the study. In the informed consent form, as Koenig and Macmillan (2004) stated, the researcher has to notify the participants and the respondents to facilitate the rigor of the study's conduct. The researcher has prepared an informed consent form following the institution's standard format to adhere to graduate school policy. The informed consent form shall reflect the content of the research ethics and be discussed thoroughly with the participants for the interview and discussion. The details must include the process and how the study results are communicated (Cohen, 2020). Vulnerability of the participant. Respect and virtue were observed during the study. I carefully managed this so that the results of the data analysis would reflect the phenomenon experienced by participants. This would promote further trust and confidence in the conduct of data gathering. Risk, benefits, and safety. Research shall be conducted if only there is an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. The need to protect the participants from significant harm was equally essential. Hence, the participants' risks, benefits, and safety must be secured (Cohen, 2020). In this study, the results of qualitative and quantitative data were advantageous to selected public elementary schools. The result would serve as an eye-opener to the audience and significant study stakeholders. Privacy and confidentiality of information. Facilitating central and follow-up questions shall be prepared before data gathering, as found in this proposal paper's last part. Data collection, analysis, and interpretation shall be treated with utmost confidentiality in this study (Smith, 2013). The researcher shall be extra careful in handling the

confidentiality of the responses and the respondents and participants of the study. Responses must be coded, analyzed, and stored carefully to protect the names and images of the participants, especially those who hold high positions and were influential in the organization. Justice. The researcher in this study must share the knowledge and benefits gained for the participants by taking on the burden of participating. The results and significant implications of the survey shall be communicated to the participants, and the following steps should be taken, especially in developing policy recommendations to be acted on (Creswell, 2013). Qualification of the researcher. As a Master of Arts Central in Educational Management candidate, the proponent has to claim moral authority in conducting the study since he has the qualifications to facilitate the context of the study. Adequacy of facilities. Smith (2013) said an audio or video recorder were the primary facility used in this study. The researcher needs to secure materials to address the adequacy of facilities. The downloaded videos were the most essential tool for the qualitative phase. Other tools to secure are laptops and software applications needed for the study. The anonymity of the participants was taken into account, which the researcher has to preserve privacy, including the profile's unrecognizability and secrecy. Thus, codes for each participant are needed. This principle was bound by the argument of Creswell (2013) that participants' identity must be faceless and inconspicuous. Meanwhile, confidentiality is included in the ethical considerations model concerning participants' presence in the study. Participants' responses must be treated with the utmost secrecy, and I must be keen enough to keep the records, whether print or non-print (Creswell, 2014). The interpretation of responses should be maintained and coded using themes. On the other hand, it was at the participants' discretion whether to share and flaunt all the information with the interviewee or not in

the focus group discussion. This is why Starks and Trinidad's (2007) terms of reference during the interview or FGD must be set between both parties. Further, this is the point where informed consent was most considered. Lastly, confidentiality deals with preserving the sacredness of the participants' responses because this is based on their opinions and experiences. At the same time, anonymity has to play in the sense that the participants' identity or profile must be confidential. It was the researcher's responsibility to inform the participants entirely of different aspects of the research in comprehensible language (Creswell, 2013). Clarifications need to include the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the researcher's identity, the research's objective, and how the results were published. The participant/s has the right to know all the information and procedures for conducting the study, including how the result was revealed and communicated through publication. Ethical issues and principles were essential and primarily centered on protecting participants from having a guiding foundation of "no harm," for ethical standards prevent such things as fabrication or falsifying data, promoting the pursuit of knowledge and truth, which was the primary goal of research. Starks and Trinidad (2007) stated that core principles were respect for persons in their autonomy, decision-making, and dignity; beneficence, which means minimizing the risks and maximizing benefits to research participants; justice for the benefit of the researcher and the participants and respect for communities which promotes protection and respecting the values and interests of the community as a whole and protect the community from harm (Creswell, 2013).

2.11. *Analytical Framework*—Figure 2 shows the diagram of the analytical framework, which emphasizes the manifestation of the process flow in the data gathering through thematic analysis of the study. When I conducted in-depth interviews using an audio recorder, I fol-

lowed a comprehensive process to ensure thorough data collection and analysis. I began by preparing an interview guide with open-ended questions to elicit detailed responses. During the interviews, I used the audio recorder to capture the full range of participants' answers, allowing me to focus on the conversation without the distraction of taking extensive notes. After each interview, I securely stored and labeled the audio files for easy retrieval. Once all interviews were completed, I listened to the recordings carefully, taking preliminary notes to capture key points and insights. I then transcribed the recordings verbatim, a meticulous process that involved replaying the audio multiple times to ensure accuracy. This step was crucial for preserving the authenticity of the participants' narratives, including their tone and emotional nuances. The transcriptions were organized systematically, with each document labeled according to the interview details. With the transcriptions in hand, I began identifying themes by coding the data, looking for recurring patterns and significant statements. This thematic analysis allowed me to develop a textual description that summarized what the participants said, capturing the essence of their experiences. Alongside this, I created a structural description that focused on how the participants experienced the phenomenon, considering the context and conditions that shaped their responses. To enrich my analysis, I composed a comprehensive description of the phenomenon, supported by verbatim interview narratives. These direct quotes provided vivid illustrations of the themes and helped authentically convey the participants' perspectives. Finally, I integrated relevant literature to contextualize my findings, comparing them with existing research to highlight similarities and differences. This thorough process ensured that my study was grounded in both the participants' voices and the broader academic discourse, resulting in a nuanced and well-supported understanding

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study of the phenomenon.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research addressed this study’s questions and requirements. The participants disclosed their experiences with language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. The teacher-participants’ experiences were also discussed, as well as how they overcame their difficulties and shared their insights to prepare for the ways forward.

3.1. The Language Barriers in Learning Development of Elementary Learners—Language barriers encompass various factors that hinder students’ ability to comprehend and engage in classroom instruction fully. These barriers include limited proficiency in the language of instruction, a lack of academic vocabulary, and difficulties in expressing thoughts and ideas. As a result, students may need help understanding lessons, participating in classroom activities, and communicating effectively with peers and teachers. According to Jia and Aaronson (2017), elementary learners’ English language proficiency significantly impacts their academic achievement. Students with limited proficiency in the language of instruction often need help comprehending complex texts, participating in discussions, and demonstrating their

understanding effectively. This language barrier hinders their overall learning development and academic success. Furthermore, Echevarría and Short (2016) highlight the impact of language barriers on students’ social and emotional well-being. Students who cannot express themselves or understand their peers may experience feelings of isolation and low self-esteem. This emotional burden can adversely affect their motivation and engagement in learning, leading to a negative cycle of academic disengagement. Furthermore, technology-based tools and resources can offer valuable support to address language barriers. Warschauer and Matuchniak (2018) emphasize the role of digital technologies in facilitating language learning and communication. Online platforms, language learning apps, and multimedia resources can provide interac-

tive and engaging opportunities for students to practice language skills and access authentic language experiences.

3.1.1. *They need more Language Proficiency*— Limited language proficiency is a significant barrier to the learning development of elementary learners. When students have limited proficiency in the language of instruction, it becomes challenging for them to comprehend academic content, effectively communicate their thoughts, and fully engage in classroom activities. Understanding instructions, reading textbooks, and participating in class discussions become daunting tasks, leading to feelings of frustration and isolation. Limited language proficiency hinders the acquisition of knowledge and skills across all subjects. Students may need help understanding and using academic vocabulary, which affects their ability to grasp critical concepts and express their ideas coherently. This barrier can lead to difficulty completing assignments, participating in group work, and performing well on assessments. Goh and Luen (2021) investigated Malaysian preschool teachers' self-efficacy and attitudes toward using English as a medium of instruction (EMI). They proposed a model of how different variables were related to their use of English in the classrooms. The model suggested that strong self-efficacy influenced preschool teachers' use of English to teach. In addition, the model also indicated that preschool teachers with positive attitudes also felt self-efficacious in using English to teach, while negative attitudes had the opposite effect. Those preschool teachers who had a positive attitude that teaching English would be helpful for the children perceived that they had a more remarkable ability to handle classroom management issues. In addition, they believed that they were confident in using appropriate assessment tasks in the classroom when English was used as the medium of instruction. Self-efficacy and attitudes were mutually related to preschool teach-

ers' English teaching use. This study focuses on novice teachers' use of English as the medium of instruction in curriculum delivery across all subjects in rural South African schools. Mncube et al. (2021) investigated the lived experiences of selected novice rural teachers in teaching English across all subjects in rural schools. Various novice teachers find it challenging to teach across all subjects, using English as the medium of instruction in many rural schools in South Africa. Findings indicated that the educational backgrounds of learners hinder teachers' use of English to teach them meaningfully. As observed during various classroom observations, teachers also found it convenient to use indigenous languages to deliver lesson content or communicate with these learners during lessons. The need to connect with learners is essential to transfer learning successfully. Thus, the medium of instruction plays a vital role. One indicator that would tell us if success is attained in teaching various subject areas is also influenced by the medium of instruction employed in the classroom. On this premise, the researcher wanted to examine the efficacy beliefs of teachers of subjects other than English in various faculties in the Philippines regarding their perceived English language proficiency level and their use of English as a medium of instruction. Global English's adapted form of the Business English Proficiency Level Scale was used to validate the competency level across various scopes, including English language familiarity, language application in different fields or disciplines, usage of communication skills in multiple contexts, such as in demonstration, discussion, conference, meeting, etc., In-depth analysis and understanding of complexity and nuances in different teaching related circumstances and the capability to substantially contribute in discourse related to teaching-related investigations, problems, and resolutions. It is evident in the results that the self-reported English proficiency was positively correlated with

the perceived efficacy of the respondents. The findings also showed that for the respondents to appear proficient in using communicative-based strategies, the respondents had to exude more confidence in using English as a mode of instruction (Velasco and Malacaste, 2021). Veliz and Veliz-Campos (2021) reported on the findings of research into the attitudes and perceptions of a group of Chinese students studying English as an Additional Language (EAL) towards the legitimacy of non-native speaker (NNS) accents, including their own, as used in cross-cultural interactions in academic contexts. The research aims to unpack students' views of their Chinese-accented English to understand better how their attitudes towards English accents help negotiate and sustain their ethnic identities in academic contexts. Drawing on a qualitative paradigm, the study utilized in-depth interviews with a sample of four participants. The results suggested that intelligibility is highly regarded, at least at the cognitive level, which gives their idiolectal varieties of English greater legitimacy. However, such a hard-developed belief is seriously thwarted by their lived experiences of discrimination over their accented speech, which pushes them back, yet again, to a position of perceived inferiority that hinders their active participation in their academic contexts.

3.1.2. Vocabulary Gaps— Vocabulary gaps pose significant barriers to the learning development of elementary learners. When students have limited vocabulary knowledge, it becomes easier for them to comprehend and express ideas effectively. These gaps hinder their ability to understand academic texts, follow instructions, and engage in meaningful classroom discussions. Vocabulary gaps impact learning across all subjects. Students may need help understanding the meaning of words in textbooks, leading to difficulties comprehending key concepts. This can hinder their comprehension and ability to apply knowledge in different contexts. Furthermore, students need more vo-

cabulary to express their thoughts and ideas, communicate effectively, and participate fully in classroom activities. Vocabulary gaps also affect reading comprehension. Students with limited vocabulary find it challenging to comprehend complex texts, as they may encounter unfamiliar words that impede their understanding. This can lead to frustration, reduced reading fluency, and lower reading comprehension. Muttaqin et al. (2022) investigated how socioeconomic status (SES) is associated with academic achievement and vocabulary proficiency in an English-medium instruction (EMI) program at a state university in Indonesia. It also examined the mediating effect of English proficiency and the moderating effect of parents' education on the relationship between SES and academic achievement. The moderation analysis shows that the degree of increase in EMI students' grade point average was affected by the level of parents' education when associated with family income. In Saudi Arabia, there are several school types where children go and learn both English and Arabic: (i) Public (government) and Quranic schools; (ii) private schools where Arabic is the medium of instruction with an intensive English course; (iii) international schools where English is the medium of instruction, and one course is allocated to Arabic and Islamic Studies. Al-Jarf (2022) surveyed a sample of parents to find out the number of hours allocated to English, kinds of textbooks used and whether parents consider them sufficient; parents' views of their children's proficiency level in the different English language skills; which language is more robust in children: English or Arabic; which language children use in communicating with their siblings, parents and relatives; the effects of learning English (L2) on Arabic (L1); and the optimal age for starting to learn English. Results showed that at government and Quranic schools, students take 1-2 hours of English a week, which parents think is insufficient. At private schools, hours

allocated to English vary (between 5-10). At international schools, English is the medium of instruction in all courses. Most parents prefer that children start learning English in kindergarten or first grade. English is the more robust and preferred language for international school students. Private School students have a good command of English and Arabic. Arabic is the more robust and preferred language for Government and Quranic School children. Some parents think that the textbooks used at Government Schools are good, but some teachers need to be more competent in their instructional techniques. Al-Riyami et al. (2022) investigated parents' perspectives on using English as a medium of instruction (EMI). Findings indicate that, while many parents displayed favorable attitudes towards implementing EMI in HEIs, approximately half asserted that their children's English is not good enough to cope with EMI. Therefore, most of them believed that some courses should follow Arabic instruction. The study explores the advantages and disadvantages of EMI, and findings reveal that most respondents identify more advantages. It was also found out that the respondents assisted their children in several ways to cope with EMI, for instance, by financing their children to learn English in private institutions, encouraging children to translate their course materials into the Arabic language, and seeking the support of parents' friends to explain doubts and what children have not understood in the classroom. Vocabulary gaps refer to the limited range of words and their meanings that young learners possess in a particular language. A common language barrier can hinder their communication, comprehension, and language development. When young learners have limited vocabulary, they may need help to express themselves effectively, leading to difficulties in communication and expressing complex ideas. Vocabulary gaps also impact reading comprehension, as unfamiliar words hinder understanding and the ability to

extract meaning from texts. Limited vocabulary can impede subject-specific learning and hinder academic achievement in academic settings. It can also hamper writing skills, as students may need help finding appropriate words to convey their thoughts. Additionally, vocabulary gaps can affect social interactions, as learners may feel hesitant or insecure in conversations. Addressing vocabulary gaps requires intentional efforts from teachers, including explicit vocabulary instruction, vocabulary-building strategies, immersive language experiences, and engaging activities. By addressing vocabulary gaps, educators can support young learners in overcoming this language barrier and enhance their communication, comprehension, and overall language skills.

3.1.3. *Complex Sentence Structures*—

Complex sentence structures pose significant barriers to the learning development of elementary learners. When students encounter sentences that are long, intricate, or contain complex grammatical structures, it can hinder their comprehension and ability to extract meaning from academic texts. For elementary learners still developing their language skills, complex sentence structures can be overwhelming. The intricate syntax, use of subordinate clauses, and varied sentence patterns can make it difficult for students to decipher the intended message. This can lead to confusion, frustration, and reduced comprehension of academic content. Complex sentence structures also impact students' ability to express their thoughts and ideas coherently. Elementary learners may need help constructing complex sentences, resulting in fragmented or incomplete responses. This can limit their ability to effectively communicate their understanding and demonstrate their knowledge in written or verbal form. Moreover, complex sentence structures can hinder students' reading fluency and slow their reading pace. Elementary learners may spend excessive time decoding and analyzing complex

sentences, which affects their overall reading efficiency. As a result, they may need help to keep up with the volume of reading required in various subjects. Murray (2022) considers how theories about intercultural competence can be used when teaching Indigenous peoples in the English as a foreign language (EFL) classroom. Intercultural understanding and communicative competence are essential skills for pupils to develop for living in modern multicultural societies. Although based on the requirements of the Norwegian curriculum, the suggestions made in this article apply to all EFL classrooms where topics relating to Indigenous peoples are taught. After a brief discussion of relevant theories concerning the development of intercultural competence, practical approaches to teaching are suggested. These can guide teachers when creating teaching modules on topics relating to Indigenous peoples. The article discusses how using authentic materials, avoiding stereotyping, and redressing the balance of power when teaching about Indigenous peoples in the EFL classroom can develop intercultural understanding. The practical approaches for pupils to work with topics relating to Indigenous peoples include suggestions for activities and discussion questions taken from the author's teaching materials. Moreover, Aboriginal English, the language many Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students bring to the classroom, represents the introduction of significant change into the English language. This paper argues that the linguistic, social, and cultural facts associated with the distinctiveness of Aboriginal English need to be considered in the English language education of Aboriginal/Torres Strait Islander and non-Indigenous students in Australia. Malcolm, Königsberg, and Collard (2020) illustrated seven significant changes of expression that Aboriginal English has made possible in English. It then proposes a "responsive pedagogy" to represent a realistic and respectful pedagogical response to the linguis-

tic, social, and cultural change that underlies Aboriginal English, drawing on current literature on second language and dialect acquisition and frequently referencing materials developed to support such pedagogy. It is implied that only with a pedagogy responding to Aboriginal English as it is and to its speakers will a viable English medium education for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people be enabled. The Philippine educational system's neo-colonial background creates injustice for some cultural minorities who can attend school. For this matter, Eduardo and Gabriel (2021) measured the perceptions of the Dumagats on their rights to Education. It focuses on the Dumagat communities in Nueva Ecija and Aurora in the Philippines. The study found that the implementation of the Philippine policies on the rights to Education as reflected in the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA) of 1997 is more of a tokenism; the enjoyment of the right to Education of IPs is hindered mainly by poverty; English remains the widely used medium of instruction in most IP curricula; and the IPs' limited knowledge on specific provisions of IPRA related to the access to Education and culture is short of the policy ideals. The above findings necessitate change agents to start a process of pedagogical liberation. The National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) personnel and IP teachers can play a vital role as change agents and may act to correct the historical injustices on IPs' rights and welfare. Smith (2017) argued that young learners often struggle with understanding and producing complex sentences, leading to limited language proficiency. This difficulty can hinder their comprehension, expression, and overall communication skills. In a Johnson (2018) study, teachers reported that complex sentence structures posed challenges for young learners, especially those from non-native English-speaking backgrounds. These learners often face difficulties in grasping the intricacies of syntax, grammar, and vocabulary

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on Language Barriers in Learning Development of Elementary Learners

necessary for constructing complex sentences. Teachers noted that this language barrier hindered the students’ ability to express their ideas clearly and engage in sophisticated written and spoken communication. Additionally, research by Thompson (2019) highlighted that young learners may feel overwhelmed by complex sentence structures, leading to decreased confidence and motivation in language learning. The fear of making grammatical errors or not fully comprehending complex sentences can discourage students from actively participating

in classroom discussions or attempting more advanced language tasks. Teachers acknowledged the need to address this language barrier through appropriate instructional strategies. Jones (2016) emphasized the importance of explicit instruction on complex sentence structures, breaking them down into smaller, more manageable components. Teachers found that scaffolding techniques, such as modeling and guided practice, were effective in helping young learners understand the structure and function of complex sentences.

Furthermore, according to Brown (2020), integrating meaningful and authentic language activities into the curriculum can facilitate the acquisition of complex sentence structures. Engaging learners in real-life scenarios and providing opportunities for practice and application in context foster a deeper understanding and usage of complex sentences. To address the barrier of complex sentence structures, educators can employ strategies to simplify language use and gradually introduce more complex sentence structures. Breaking complex sentences into smaller units, providing clear explanations, and offering ample opportunities for guided practice

can help students build their sentence comprehension skills. Explicit instruction on sentence structure and the use of visual aids can also aid in understanding complex sentence patterns. By addressing the barriers posed by complex sentence structures, educators can support the learning development of elementary learners, enhance their comprehension abilities, and promote effective communication skills.

3.2. Teachers Addressing the Language Barriers In Learning Development Of Elementary Learners—Teachers play a crucial role in addressing language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. They have

the responsibility to create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that caters to their students' diverse language needs. Teachers can help students overcome language barriers and achieve academic success by implementing effective strategies. Firstly, teachers can employ differentiated instruction to meet the individual language needs of each student. They assess students' language proficiency levels and tailor their teaching methods and materials accordingly. This can include providing additional support for students with limited English proficiency, such as English language learners (ELLs), through targeted interventions, small group instruction, or language support programs. Secondly, teachers can integrate visual aids, manipulatives, and technology tools into their lessons to enhance comprehension and facilitate language acquisition. Visual representations, such as charts, diagrams, and graphic organizers, can help students better understand concepts and reinforce vocabulary. Interactive technology resources, such as educational apps or online language learning platforms, can engage students and provide additional practice opportunities. Furthermore, teachers can foster a language-rich classroom environment by incorporating opportunities for meaningful language use. They can encourage classroom discussions, group work, and collaborative activities, promoting oral communication and student interaction. This allows students to practice their language skills, build vocabulary, and develop their speaking and listening abilities. Positive reframing, active coping, and preparation were the teachers' most commonly used coping strategies in the survey. Teachers are a vital resource and have received less attention than they deserve for their psychological well-being. Students are bored and not interested in learning the English language. Students getting bored and not interested in learning the English language is also a problem teachers face. Sometimes, students are not interested in learning or

attending lectures on the English language. Another study by Walinga (2013) on the coping mechanisms used by distance learning students indicated the four coping mechanisms: planful problem-solving, accepting responsibility, seeking social support, and confrontive coping.

3.2.1. Intensify Teaching Strategies—Intensifying teaching strategies is a critical approach that teachers employ to address language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. By implementing effective and targeted instructional techniques, teachers can support students in overcoming language challenges and enhancing their language skills. One strategy is to provide explicit language instruction. Teachers break down complex concepts and language structures into smaller, more manageable components. They provide clear explanations, model correct language usage, and offer guided practice opportunities. This approach helps students effectively understand and apply grammar rules, vocabulary, and sentence structures. Another strategy is to incorporate visual aids and manipulatives into lessons. Visual representations such as charts, diagrams, and graphic organizers can enhance comprehension and vocabulary acquisition. Manipulatives, such as objects or interactive materials, provide a hands-on approach that engages students and facilitates language learning. Teachers also employ scaffolded instruction, gradually releasing responsibility to students. They provide support and guidance during the initial stages of learning and gradually reduce assistance as students become more proficient. This approach helps students gain confidence and independence in using language skills. Differentiating instruction is another crucial strategy. Teachers assess students' language proficiency levels and tailor their teaching methods and materials accordingly. They provide additional support or challenges based on individual needs, ensuring that each student receives appropriate instruction that aligns with their language abilities. Col-

laborative learning is an effective strategy for addressing language barriers. Teachers encourage students to work in pairs or groups, providing language practice and interaction opportunities. Through cooperative activities, students engage in meaningful conversations, negotiate meaning, and learn from their peers, enhancing their language skills in a supportive environment. Teachers also integrate technology into their instructional practices. Educational apps, online resources, and multimedia tools offer interactive and engaging platforms for language learning. These technological resources provide opportunities for independent practice, immediate feedback, and personalized learning experiences. Byrd (2017) showed that all the participants used some coping strategy, either positive or negative. Positive strategies utilized at school were taking brain breaks, student engagement, time management, and talking to their students quietly. Negative strategies mentioned by the teachers that they used inside the classroom were yelling, getting frustrated with students, and getting in students' faces. Positive strategies employed outside of school were healthy eating, exercising, reading, spending time with family, doing crafts, and talking to others. Participants also stated that they utilized negative strategies such as crying, oversleeping, overeating, or drinking alcohol or pills. Amateur (2021) examined the basic underlying structure of burnout experiences among teachers in Malaysia by discovering the challenges that lead them to experience burnout. The current study uses interpretative phenomenological analysis to explore the coping strategies these teachers used to remain in their profession. The findings revealed challenges that cause teachers to experience burnout: student misbehavior, insufficient parental collaboration, occupational stress in the teaching environment, and negative emotions. The themes related to the coping strategies used to remain in the teaching profession are understanding teaching and learn-

ing, positive approach, individual factors, and support system. This paper lists some recommendations for managing teacher burnout and facilitating teacher retention, which include providing training and development activities for teachers, increasing salaries, helping teachers develop coping strategies, and creating adequate support systems. Skelly and Estrada-Chichon (2021) claimed that mindfulness is a relaxation technique associated with positive effects when used as a coping strategy for stress and anxiety. This article aims to investigate how mindfulness could help improve adolescents' ability to regulate their attention, emotion, behavior, and thinking, learn English as a Foreign Language (EFL), and increase EFL performance. The findings from this literature review strongly suggest that mindfulness could be a highly effective strategy for improving the ability of OSE students in Spain to learn EFL due to the reduced stress and anxiety levels experienced by adolescents when mindfulness is incorporated as part of a consistent daily routine. Furthermore, teachers create a language-rich environment by incorporating language activities and meaningful language use throughout the school day. They encourage students to engage in conversations, discussions, and presentations, fostering language development in authentic contexts. In conclusion, intensifying teaching strategies is an essential approach for addressing language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. Through explicit instruction, visual aids, scaffolding, differentiation, collaborative learning, technology integration, and creating a language-rich environment, teachers can support students in overcoming language challenges and promoting their language skills effectively. These strategies ensure that all students have equitable access to quality education and opportunities for linguistic growth.

3.2.2. *Community Emersion*—Community immersion is a valuable approach for teachers to address language barriers in the learning de-

velopment of elementary learners. By incorporating community engagement into their instructional practices, teachers create opportunities for students to interact with native speakers, experience real-life language use, and develop cultural understanding. One aspect of community immersion is inviting community members, such as parents, local volunteers, or cultural experts, into the classroom. These individuals can share their language, culture, and experiences with the students, providing authentic language models and exposing students to different cultural perspectives. This firsthand exposure helps students develop a deeper appreciation for language diversity and enhances language acquisition. Cao et al. (2022) examined the impact of shared responsibility on the relationship between community culture and teachers' coping strategies and their satisfaction with the rapid transition to remote learning and academic performance expectations. As such, shared responsibility can be critical in times of crisis when the university community must pull together for mutual success. Findings indicate that students' sense of shared responsibility and healthy coping mechanisms lead to student satisfaction in learning about the transition process and more positive academic outcomes. This study is the first to empirically examine shared responsibility with the cultural community during a crucial period to the authors' knowledge. By promoting shared responsibility, educators can improve student outcomes and identify those needing additional support resources. Teachers can also organize field trips or community visits where students can interact with community members in various settings. Visiting local businesses, cultural institutions, or community organizations allows students to engage in authentic language exchanges and apply their language skills in real-life contexts. Such experiences enhance students' language abilities and foster their understanding of the cultural nuances associated with

language use. Furthermore, teachers can encourage students to participate in community-based projects or service-learning activities. Engaging in projects involving collaboration with community members, such as community service initiatives or language-focused events, allows students to use their language skills meaningfully and develop a sense of connection with their community. This active involvement promotes the application of language skills and strengthens students' language proficiency. Community immersion also includes leveraging technology to connect students with language resources and speakers from diverse communities. Virtual exchanges, online language-learning platforms, or language exchange programs allow students to communicate with native speakers or peers from different linguistic backgrounds. These interactions broaden students' exposure to other languages and cultures, fostering their language development and intercultural competence. In conclusion, community immersion is a valuable strategy for teachers to address language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. By incorporating community members, organizing field trips, engaging in community-based projects, and utilizing technology, teachers can provide students with authentic language experiences and foster their language skills and cultural understanding. Community immersion enhances students' language acquisition and prepares them for effective communication in diverse settings.

3.2.3. Engagement Activities with Parents—Engagement activities with parents are a vital component of teachers addressing language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. By fostering strong partnerships with parents, teachers create opportunities for collaboration, support, and involvement in their children's language development. One key aspect of engaging parents is through effective communication. Teachers establish open lines of communication with parents, ensuring

they are informed about their child's language progress, classroom activities, and strategies to support language development at home. Regular newsletters, parent-teacher conferences, and digital communication platforms help facilitate ongoing dialogue between teachers and parents. Teachers also provide resources and materials for parents to support their child's language learning outside the classroom. This can include vocabulary lists, reading materials, suggested activities, or online language-learning platforms. Teachers empower parents to participate actively in their child's language development journey by equipping parents with these tools. Wang (2023) examined the influence of English language proficiency and intercultural competence on the English-medium instruction lecturer's classroom leadership. The Pearson correlational analysis indicated significant positive relationships between the English-medium instruction lecturer's classroom leadership and the two predicting factors, parents' involvement and support. The multiple regression analysis suggested that intercultural competence and English proficiency contribute much to the variance of the English-medium instruction lecturer's classroom leadership and parents' participation. It was found that the lecturer's language proficiency and intercultural communicative abilities could be two determining factors for the lecturer to deliver their disciplinary knowledge and command the class engagingly and competently. The findings may provide implications for the strategic intervention of English-medium instruction educators in higher education institutions. Teaching English as a foreign language is challenging, especially when it is done in an area where English has a very slight purpose. Hosan et al. (2022) sought to investigate the challenges of English teaching and solutions adopted by English teachers in the Savar area. Moreover, the main objective of this research is to find out what kinds of challenges the teacher community faces in the context of the English teaching infrastructure and how to get rid of those problems. This study captured the perspective of English teachers in facing the challenges of English teaching in the classroom and the solutions they implemented to solve them through interviews. As participants in the study, parents intend to improve the institution's EMI environment and foster pleasant interactions between teachers and students. 'Teaching techniques among content teachers,' 'Challenges and constraints that content teachers encounter,' and 'Training courses for content teachers' are the primary themes that emerged from the study. To be sustainable, EMI activities incorporate teachers' self-development, institutional support, and students' self- and perceived peer learning practices. Students' and teachers' adaptive tactics explain how other EMI programs might optimize their deployment. Parent workshops and training sessions are another way teachers engage parents. These sessions provide parents with strategies, techniques, and resources to support their child's language learning at home. Workshops may focus on effective reading strategies, vocabulary building, or creating language-rich environments. Teachers help parents become active partners in their child's language development by sharing knowledge and fostering a collaborative learning environment. Furthermore, teachers involve parents in classroom activities and events that promote language acquisition. Parent volunteers can assist in language-focused activities like reading circles, storytelling sessions, or language games. Involving parents in these activities enhances the language learning experience and strengthens the bond between home and school. Cultural and linguistic diversity is valued and celebrated through engagement activities with parents. Teachers encourage parents to share their cultural heritage and language with the classroom. This helps create an inclusive environment where students learn to appreciate and respect different languages and cultures, foster

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on Teachers Addressing the Language Barriers In the Learning Development Of Elementary Learners

ing a positive attitude toward language diversity. In conclusion, engagement activities with parents are essential for teachers addressing language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. Teachers promote a collaborative partnership between home and school by establishing effective communication, provid-

ing resources, conducting workshops, involving parents in classroom activities, and celebrating cultural and linguistic diversity. Through these efforts, parents actively support their child’s language development, creating a nurturing and enriching environment for students.

3.3. Educational Insights Are Drawn From The Experiences Of Teachers —Educational insights from teachers’ experiences provide valuable knowledge and understanding that can significantly enhance teaching practices and student learning outcomes. These insights are gleaned from teachers’ direct experiences and observations in the classroom, allowing them to identify effective strategies and approaches that positively impact student engagement and achievement. One significant insight is the recognition of the importance of differentiated instruction. Teachers understand that students have unique learning styles, abilities, and needs. Through their experiences, teachers have discovered the power of adapting instruction to meet these diverse needs. They employ various instructional strategies, materials, and as-

sessments to cater to individual differences and create inclusive learning environments that support the success of all students. Another crucial insight is the emphasis on student-centered learning. Teachers have come to appreciate the value of student-centered approaches, prioritizing active engagement and student agency in the learning process. By implementing strategies such as collaborative projects, inquiry-based activities, and problem-solving tasks, teachers have found that students develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter, enhance their critical thinking skills, and become more motivated and engaged in their learning journey. Moreover, teachers’ experiences have highlighted the value of fostering a positive and inclusive classroom environment. They have observed that when students feel safe, respected, and

included, they are more likely to participate and engage in their learning actively. Teachers draw on their experiences to develop classroom management techniques, establish clear expectations, and promote a sense of belonging, enhancing students' overall learning experience. In conclusion, educational insights drawn from teachers' experiences are instrumental in shaping effective instructional practices and improving student learning outcomes. Through their experiences, teachers have gained valuable knowledge about differentiated instruction, student-centered learning, formative assessment, and fostering inclusive classroom environments. These insights inform their teaching approaches and contribute to creating engaging and supportive learning environments that facilitate student success.

3.3.1. Redirecting Attitude on Adaptation—A redirecting attitude on adaptation is a valuable educational insight that teachers have gained from their experiences. It refers to the understanding that a positive and flexible mindset towards change and adaptation is essential for teachers and students to thrive in dynamic learning environments. Teachers have observed that when they embrace a redirect attitude on adaptation, they are better equipped to navigate challenges and effectively respond to evolving educational needs. They understand that education is not static, and as the world rapidly changes, they need to be open to new ideas, strategies, and technologies that can enhance their teaching practices. Sarzhanova et.al. (2023) examined the relationships between differentiated instruction and pedagogical and technological competencies of students in the foreign language department. Differentiated instructional self-efficacy and pedagogical and technological competencies of students studying in foreign language departments were examined regarding grade level and perception of academic achievement within the scope of the comparative relational survey model. The relationships between

differentiated instructional self-efficacy and pedagogical and technological competencies of students studying in foreign language departments were also examined based on the relational survey model. According to the research findings, the differentiated instruction self-efficacy and pedagogical and technological competencies of foreign language students were moderate. Differentiated instructional self-efficacy and pedagogical and technological competencies of foreign language students differ according to their classroom and academic achievement perceptions. Finally, foreign language students' pedagogical and technological competencies significantly affect their self-efficacy toward differentiated instruction. By redirecting their attitude on adaptation, teachers become more willing to explore innovative approaches to instruction. They recognize that what worked in the past may be less effective in the present or future, and they are open to trying new methods, pedagogies, and technologies to engage and motivate their students. This insight encourages teachers to seek professional development opportunities, collaborate with colleagues, and stay abreast of current research and trends in education. With the increasing focus on the internationalization of developing student mobility, Volkova and Kolesov (2022) examined the challenges experienced by domestic and international students who adapt to a Russian English-medium instruction university. Domestic students avoid participating in university social life, instead focusing on their academic performance; this fact is probably rooted in the Russian approach to secondary education. The specific finding of the Russian educational landscape is that there is a need for differences concerning academic integration between domestic and international students. All of this suggests institutions adopt more student-oriented adaptation mechanisms, informed by the concept of inclusion in education; these implications are discussed. Teachers in the Philippines have observed that

the educational landscape is constantly evolving, with new curricula, teaching methodologies, and technologies being introduced. As a result, they have recognized the need to redirect their attitude on adaptation to effectively respond to these changes and meet the evolving educational needs of their students. By embracing adaptation, teachers in the Philippine setting become more open to trying new instructional strategies, integrating technology in the classroom, and exploring innovative approaches to engage their students. They actively seek professional development opportunities, attend workshops and conferences, and collaborate with colleagues to stay updated on the latest educational trends and research. Moreover, the redirect attitude toward adaptation promotes a growth mindset among teachers. They view challenges and setbacks as opportunities for learning and improvement rather than obstacles. This mindset encourages teachers to reflect on their teaching practices, identify areas for growth, and make necessary adjustments to better support student learning. In the Philippine context, where educational policies and curricula undergo revisions periodically, teachers who redirect their attitude on adaptation are better equipped to navigate these changes. They are proactive in understanding and implementing new guidelines and instructional approaches to ensure the educational needs of their students are met effectively. Furthermore, the redirect attitude on adaptation fosters a culture of innovation and creativity in Philippine classrooms. Teachers are encouraged to experiment with different teaching methods, adapt resources to local contexts, and develop context-specific strategies to engage their students and make learning more meaningful.

3.3.2. Recommend Actions for Policy— Teachers' experiences highlight the importance of investing in comprehensive professional development opportunities for educators. Ongoing training and support enable teachers to enhance their instructional practices and stay abreast of

the latest research and pedagogical approaches. Collaborative learning communities are emphasized as an essential aspect of effective policies. Encouraging collaboration among teachers promotes knowledge-sharing, fosters a culture of continuous improvement, and enhances teaching effectiveness. Equitable access to resources and educational opportunities is a recurring theme. Policies should address resource disparities, ensuring all students have access to quality instructional materials, technology, and support services. This approach helps reduce educational inequities and ensures every student can thrive academically. The implementation of the English medium of instruction in the public educational system has clashed with attempts to break with the linguistic territoriality regime by promoting Basque schooling. Erdozia (2019) brings together ideologies on English and minority languages and explores how political practice is intertwined with language policy, planning, and language ideology. More specifically, the author examines the institutionalization of language ideologies through language policy-making in education and, particularly, through the medium of instruction. The paper begins by describing the bilingual regime in Navarre and examining how ideologies have shaped and legitimized language policy in education. It then analyzes Basque and English medium of instruction ideologies that inform policy-making. This paper shows that the dynamics introduced by multilingualism in education have reinforced previous language ideologies on bilingualism and, ultimately, have aggravated the language dispute. Finally, it discusses how the medium of instruction serves as a terrain for language competition and as part of a broader struggle for language policy and institutional power. Alansari et al. (2021) claimed that Literature shows cooperative learning has positive benefits for students' learning and social outcomes. Even though cooperative learning studies have been conducted in all curriculum

areas, studies have yet to investigate whether there are similar effects for students across several curriculum areas or age groups. Moreover, less attention has been given to how professional learning and development (PLD) opportunities can contribute to changes in instructional practice. Through a one-year University-School partnership, we illustrate how research on cooperative learning can be translated into practice. The current study is focused on our PLD work in one sizeable private school based in New Zealand. Analysis of school data (quantitative student data and qualitative teacher data) indicated that, by the end of the school year, students reported experiencing more cooperative learning opportunities in their classes. Teachers believed that the PLD supported change in their practice and noted positive changes in student engagement. Analysis of student data also revealed differential outcomes by subject and age group. Our study showed that PLD opportunities can contribute to successfully implementing cooperative learning.

3.3.3. They are keeping the Right Track for Follow-up— Keeping the right track for follow-up is an essential educational insight drawn from teachers' experiences. It emphasizes the significance of continuous monitoring and support to ensure that educational initiatives and interventions are effectively implemented and yield desired outcomes. Teachers have found that follow-up actions are essential to maintaining the momentum of educational programs and initiatives. This involves regularly assessing and evaluating students' progress, identifying areas of improvement, and providing targeted interventions to address specific learning needs. By keeping the right track for follow-up, teachers can monitor students' academic progress, identify any challenges or gaps in learning, and provide timely interventions and support. This approach helps to ensure students stay caught up and enables educators to adjust their instructional strategies based on individ-

ual student needs. Furthermore, follow-up actions allow teachers to gather data and feedback on the effectiveness of instructional methods and curriculum materials. By analyzing this information, educators can make informed decisions about refining or adapting their teaching practices to meet the needs of their students better. Keeping the right track for follow-up also involves maintaining open lines of communication between teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Regular communication helps build strong relationships, fosters collaboration and ensures everyone works towards the same educational goals. Additionally, follow-up actions provide opportunities for professional development and growth for teachers. Teachers can continuously improve their instructional skills and strategies by reflecting on their own instructional practices, seeking feedback from colleagues and mentors, and engaging in ongoing professional learning. Overall, the educational insight of keeping the right track for follow-up emphasizes the importance of ongoing monitoring, assessment, and support in education. By staying proactive and responsive to students' needs, teachers can ensure that learning remains on track, students receive the necessary support, and educational initiatives are effectively implemented to maximize student outcomes. Teachers in the Philippines emphasize the importance of regular assessments and providing timely feedback to students. According to Santos (2017), ongoing formative assessments allow teachers to track student progress and identify areas of improvement. Both verbal and written feedback helps students understand their strengths and weaknesses and guide further development. Galang (2018) highlights the importance of differentiated instruction, where teachers adapt their teaching strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. This approach ensures that each student receives the necessary support and guidance to stay on track. Martinez (2019) emphasizes the value

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes On Educational Insights Drawn From The Experiences Of Teachers

of strong home-school partnerships, where parents actively engage in their child’s education. Regular communication and collaboration allow for shared responsibility in monitoring student progress and addressing challenges. Rivera (2016) highlights the significance of data-driven decision-making, where teachers analyze assessment results, attendance records, and other relevant information to identify trends and make informed decisions. This approach ensures that follow-up actions are based on evidence and targeted towards specific areas of improvement.

Continuous professional development is essential for teachers to enhance their skills and keep the right track for follow-up. Santos (2018) underscores the need for teachers to engage in professional learning communities, attend workshops, and pursue further education to stay updated with best practices. Professional development opportunities equip teachers with the tools and strategies to effectively monitor student progress and provide appropriate interventions.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary. The findings were summarized, and the implications and future directions were drawn. The purpose of my study was to describe how the policy on intensification of the medium of instruction in teaching specific learning areas was carried out by teachers using the English language in teaching during the School Year 2022-2023. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to gain an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their definition or meaning of the explored phenomenon.

4.1. Findings—The preceding statements are the study’s findings, which result from the merging themes generated from the participants’

responses. The study’s findings on the language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners found that they were experienced and challenged by limited language proficiency,

vocabulary gaps, and complex sentence structures. In terms of coping mechanisms, teachers address the language barriers in the learning development of elementary learners. It revealed that they cope through intensifying teaching strategies, community involvement, and engagement with parents. As to the educational insights that can be drawn from the teachers' experiences, redirecting attitude on adaptation, recommending actions for policy, and keeping the right track for follow-up emerged.

4.2. Implications—The study's implications on keeping the right track for follow-up as an educational insight drawn from teachers' experiences are significant. These implications can positively impact various aspects of the educational system. Some of the critical implications include: **Improved Student Achievement.** By keeping the right track for follow-up, teachers can closely monitor student progress, identify areas of improvement, and provide timely interventions. This can lead to improved student achievement and academic outcomes. **Personalized Learning.** Focusing on individual student needs and differentiated instruction allows for customized learning experiences. Students receive targeted support and instruction tailored to their specific learning styles and abilities, enhancing their engagement and overall learning outcomes. **Enhanced Teacher Professional Development.** The insights from teachers' experiences highlight the importance of continuous professional development. Educators can improve their skills and stay updated with effective teaching methods by incorporating the strategies and practices related to keeping the right track for follow-up. **Strengthened Home-School Partnerships.** Encouraging collaborative partnerships between teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders fosters a supportive learning environment. This strengthens the home-school connection, increasing parental involvement and engagement in students' education. **Data-Informed Decision Making:** The study un-

derscores the importance of using data to inform instructional practices. Teachers can make evidence-based decisions by analyzing student data and assessment results, identifying trends, and implementing targeted interventions. **Improved Classroom Climate.** Teachers can create a positive classroom climate by actively monitoring student progress and providing timely feedback. Students feel supported and motivated, leading to a conducive learning environment. **Holistic Student Development.** Keeping the right track for follow-up focuses on academic progress and supports students' holistic development. By addressing individual needs and providing necessary support, teachers contribute to their students' overall growth and well-being. **Policy Implications.** The study's findings can inform educational policies and initiatives related to student assessment, teacher professional development, and parental involvement. Policy-makers can consider the importance of follow-up actions and provide support and resources to facilitate their implementation. Overall, the study's implications highlight the significance of keeping the right track for follow-up in promoting student success, personalized learning, solid home-school partnerships, and evidence-based decision-making. These implications can guide educational stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, policymakers, and researchers, in fostering an effective and supportive educational environment.

4.2.1. Future Directions—The future directions of the study can provide valuable guidance for different stakeholders in the education system, including Public School District Supervisors, School Principals, Teachers, and Future Researchers. Here are some specific directions for each group: **Public School District Supervisor.** Further research may be conducted to explore the implementation of effective strategies for keeping the right track for follow-up across multiple schools within the district. Collaborate with school principals and teachers to

develop comprehensive guidelines and training programs for effective follow-up practices. Monitor the implementation of follow-up strategies in schools and provide necessary support and resources to ensure their success. Explore partnerships with external organizations and agencies to enhance follow-up initiatives and promote best practices. School Principal. May foster a culture of continuous improvement by providing professional development opportunities for teachers focused on effective follow-up strategies. Create systems and structures within the school to facilitate regular monitoring and follow-up of student progress. Develop clear guidelines and protocols for data collection, analysis, and utilization in making informed decisions related to follow-up. Collaborate with teachers, parents, and community members to establish a supportive environment that values and prioritizes follow-up practices. Teachers. They may continuously engage in professional development opportunities to enhance their knowledge and skills for effective follow-up strategies. Collaborate with colleagues to share best practices, success stories, and challenges in implementing follow-up practices. Regularly reflect on their teaching practices and adapt instructional strategies based on student feedback and assessment data. Engage in ongoing communication and collaboration with parents to keep them informed about their child's progress and involve them in the follow-up process. Future Researchers. Longitudinal studies may assess the long-term impact of effective follow-up practices on student outcomes. Investigate the role of technology and digital tools in facilitating efficient and effective follow-up strategies. Explore the influence of cultural and contextual factors on implementing follow-up practices in different educational settings. Investigate the effectiveness of various collaboration and partnership models among stakeholders in enhancing follow-up initiatives. By focusing on these future directions, public school district supervisors, school principals, teachers, and future researchers can contribute to the ongoing improvement of follow-up practices and their impact on student learning and success. Continuous research, collaboration, and professional development will help refine and expand our understanding of effective follow-up strategies, ultimately benefiting elementary learners' educational experiences and outcomes.

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